

The Influence of Job Stress, Workload, and Job Satisfaction on Employee Turnover Intention In The Logistics Companies

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Abstract- Human resources are a strategic factor in all institutional or organizational activities. Human resources must be managed properly so that the company can compete with other company. One of the problems that affects the workforce in a company is the high turnover rate. This study aims to determine the effect of work stress, workload, and job satisfaction on employee turnover intention at The Logistics Companies in Jember Regency. The population in the study were all employees of The Logistic Companies in Jember Regency totaling 148 people and 108 respondent with using the Isaac and Michel formula for generating sample. The data used in this study are primary data and secondary data. The research method used is multiple liner regression. The results of this study indicate that work stress has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention, workload has a positive and insignificant effect on turnover intention, job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. And work stress, workload, and job satisfaction simultaneously and significantly affect turnover intention.

Keywords: Job Stress, Workload, Job Satisfaction, Turnover Intention.

I. Introduction

One of the problems affecting the workforce in a company is the high *turnover* rate. *Turnover* or labor *turnover* is the real result of *turnover intention* which is a serious problem for company. Putra (2016) explains that *turnover intention* is a person's intention to leave his job due to the dissatisfaction felt by employees and creates a desire to leave the current job and look for another job. The high *turnover* rate will have a negative impact on the company, among others, creating high HR management costs which include the cost of training that employees have done to recruitment and retraining for new employees (Sartika, 2014).

Based on previous research conducted by Riani & Putra (2017); Silalahi (2019); and Fitriantini *et.al* (2020) where the results showed that work stress and workload variables had a positive and significant effect on *turnover intention*. In addition to work stress and load that affect *turnover intention*, job satisfaction can also affect it, this is supported by research from Saeka & Suana (2016); Monica & Putra (2017); Rijasawitri & Suana (2020) where the results showed a negative effect on job satisfaction variables on *turnover intention*. Based on several studies, it can be concluded that the causes of *turnover intention* are influenced by job stress, workload, and job satisfaction.

Job stress is a symptom or feeling that arises in individuals related to the demands or pressures faced at work and can have an impact on an organization or company, it will also affect employee satisfaction which will affect performance decline (Chaundry, 2012). If job stress increases, it will lead to a desire in employees to leave the company (Chandio *et.al*, 2013).

Workload is a job condition with a job description that must be completed within a predetermined time limit. According to Achyana (2016) workload is the capacity of work that must be done by an organizational unit and is the result between work volume and time norms. Every employee certainly has a different perception of workload, but the higher the workload felt by someone will certainly give a negative perception of his job, it causes someone to have the intention to leave his current job and look for a better job than before.

Job satisfaction is a pleasant or unpleasant emotional feeling felt by employees in view of their work. Robbins & Judge (2017:146) state that job satisfaction is the general attitude of an individual or employee towards his job. Job satisfaction is a condition related to the emotional reaction from the view of a person who has gotten his needs from the work done, so that if the employee feels that his needs are met, the employee will stay in the company because he feels comfortable at work, but on the contrary, if the employee's needs are not met, the employee will leave the company.

From the results of interviews and data on employee *turnover* rates obtained from the company, it was found that almost every month the company experienced *turnover*. In January - August 2022 the *turnover* rate that occurred in The Logistics Companies in Jember Regency was 27.5%. Edward Roesman in Rostiana (2017) states that if the company's turnover reaches 10%, the company's *turnover* category is said to be high.

The stress felt by employees is because employees often get complaints from consumers because of long deliveries, even though this long delivery is not due to deliberate but due to *overload delivery*, but consumers do not understand it. In addition, there are also frequent rejections of COD (cash on delivery) packages at the recipient. As a result, there is an accumulation of returned packages in the warehouse, so that employees must sort out the packages to be returned again, this will also hamper the delivery of packages that have previously entered. Research conducted by Salama *et al* (2022) shows that job stress has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention.

Employees are required to be able to deliver goods according to a predetermined target but the time given is limited, employees must solve these problems without being given solutions such as additional time, if they exceed working hours, employees are usually asked to work overtime so that the target for that day is achieved. In addition, employees must be able to deliver packages according to the estimated time even though when in the field there are many obstacles such as traffic jams, *overloaded* shipments if they exceed the estimated time usually employees will be blamed, then employees are required to keep the package/goods perfect. By keeping the package perfect, employees must work carefully and that takes time while employees work with time demands. Research conducted by Masta and Riyanto (2020) shows that workload affects turnover intention.

Employees need a sense of satisfaction in carrying out their work. Employees feel satisfaction with compensation in the form of wages to their employees. Then when employees do work beyond the limit of working hours, employees also get incentives from the office. So that this satisfaction can support employees' desire to leave the company due to stress and perceived workload. This is certainly a factor that makes employees feel cared for at work. Research conducted by Zhang, Bian, Bai, Kong, Liu, Cheng, and Li (2020) shows that job satisfaction has a negative effect on turnover intention.

II. LITERATUR REVIEW

Job Stress

In general, job stress is a problem that is often associated with events in the work environment, such as the process of interaction between an employee and several aspects of his job that have incompatible characteristics, as well as unclear changes in the company. Job stress can also be interpreted as pressure, tension or also unpleasant disturbances that come from outside a person. Meanwhile, Handoko (2012: 200) also suggests that stress is a demand on a person, related to objects in the environment or a stimulus that is objectively at risk. So much stress can also threaten individual resilience to deal with conditions in the work environment. Job stress is also a form of emotional pressure experienced by employees in carrying out work.

Workload

Workload is something that arises from the relationship between task demands derived from the work environment, skills and perceptions of employees. Workload is sometimes operationally defined in terms of factors such as task demands or the pressure of working hours to get the job done.

Munandar (2013: 85) explains that workload is the capability of a person in accepting work. The quantity of work also needs to be adjusted to the number of employees available, each workload obtained by employees should be balanced against physical abilities, cognitive abilities and limitations of a person in getting the load.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is not how hard an employee works or how easy it is for someone to work, but how much an employee likes the job. Job satisfaction is related to a person's feelings or attitudes towards his job, salary, promotion or education opportunities, supervision, work colleagues, workload, and others. According to Koesmono (2014) states that job satisfaction is an assessment, feeling or attitude of an employee regarding his work related to the work environment, namely the fulfillment of several needs and desires through work. From the above understanding, it can be concluded that job satisfaction is a pleasant psychological condition felt by employees in a work environment due to adequate fulfillment of needs.

Job satisfaction is a positive feeling about an individual's job that is obtained from evaluating the characteristics of the job itself (Robbins and Judge, 2017:75). This attitude is reflected by work morale. Meanwhile, according to Sunyoto (2012), job satisfaction is an individual human trait so that everyone has different levels of satisfaction according to the values that apply in themselves.

Turnover Intention

Definition of *Turnover Intention*

A person's intention to leave or move (*turnover intention*) is a person's tendency to leave the current workplace and choose another job alternative. The intention to leave work leads to the final reality faced by the company in the form of many employees leaving the company. This can occur due to the influence of the workload received by employees that is too high, or the influence of work stress experienced by each employee, even suspected due to work conflicts that occur in the company which results in employees getting emotional fatigue so that employees have low commitment to the company and the intention to change jobs appears.

Desire or (*intention*) is an intention that grows within a person to get something. Meanwhile, (*turnover*) is the exit of an employee from his place of work by voluntarily or moving from one place of work to another. According to Hartono (2014:76), if an employee does not get job satisfaction in the company, the psychological maturity of the employee will never be achieved, and turns into a feeling of frustration due to many factors and in the end there is a desire to leave the company or what is called *turnover intention*, this can interfere with the company in achieving its goals.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework is the relationship or relationship between a variable and other variables of the problem under study. This conceptual framework is expected to help examine whether there is an effect of work stress, workload, and job satisfaction that may affect *turnover intention*. The relationship between these variables can be described in a conceptual framework as Figure 1 follows:

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Description: Partially affected
 Simultaneously influenced

Hypothesis Development

According to Sugiyono (2018:63) the research hypothesis is a temporary answer or conjecture obtained from research problems, where this research problem is arranged in the form of a question sentence based on a strong theoretical basis and supported by the results of relevant research. Based on the theory and research results first, the research hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

The Effect of Job Stress on *Turnover Intention*

Based on the results of research conducted by Fitriantini *et.al* (2020) conducted on health workers with contract status, job stress has a positive effect on *turnover intention*. Meanwhile, research conducted by Saeka & Suana (2016); Monica & Putra (2017); Riani & Putra (2017); Yuda & Ardana (2017); Rijasawitri & Suana (2020); Kristin *et.al* (2022) resulted in a positive influence between job stress on *turnover intention*. Based on this exposure, a hypothesis can be formulated, namely:

H1 : Job stress affects *Turnover intention* of permanent employees at The Logistic Companies in Jember Regency.

The Effect of Workload on *Turnover Intention*

Based on research conducted by Riani & Putra (2017); Sakul (2018); Kristin (2022) found that there is a positive relationship between workload and *turnover intention*, then Fitriantini *et.al's* research (2020) conducted on contract health workers found that workload has a positive effect on *turnover intention*, besides that there is also research by Dwi & Verina (2015); Gayatri & Muttaqiyathun (2020); Khomariyah *et.al* (2020) which found that workload has a simultaneous and significant effect on *turnover intention*. Based on this description, the following hypothesis can be drawn:

H2 : Workload affects *Turnover intention* of permanent employees at The Logistic Companies in Jember Regency.

The Effect of Job Satisfaction on *Turnover Intention*

Based on the results of research conducted by Saeka & Suana (2016); Monica & Putra (2017); Yuda & Ardana (2017); Sakul (2018); Rijasawitri and Suana (2020); Fitriantini *et.al* (2020) found that there is a negative relationship between job satisfaction and *turnover intention*. Then Gayatri & Muttaqiyathun's research (2020); Khomariyah *et.al* (2020; Kristin *et.al* (2022) found that job satisfaction affects *turnover intention*. Based on this description, the following hypothesis can be drawn:

H3 : Job satisfaction affects *Turnover intention* of permanent employees at The Logistic Companies in Jember Regency.

The Effect of Job Stress, Workload, and Job Satisfaction on *Turnover Intention*

Based on the results of research conducted by Dwi and Verina (2015) in their research, it states that there is a simultaneous influence of work stress, workload, and work environment on *turnover intention*. Research conducted by Silalahi (2019) resulted in workload, work stress, and work conflict having a simultaneous influence on *turnover intention*. Miftahur *et.al* (2021) also prove that there is a simultaneous and significant influence between workload, job satisfaction, and job stress on *turnover intention*.

III. Research Methodology

Research Design

The type of research used in this research is *explanatory* research which explains the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable by knowing the cause and effect. The approach used in this research is a quantitative approach. This study will analyze the effect of work stress, workload, and job satisfaction on employee *turnover intention* at The Logistic Companies in Jember Regency.

Population and Sample

According to Sugiyono (2018:130) population is a generalization area consisting of objects / subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics that are applied by researchers to study and then draw conclusions. The research method used in this research is descriptive and verification analysis and operating the calculations using smartPLS Version 3.2. This research was conducted at

PT. PLN Pusharlis (Persero), which is located at Jalan Banten No. 10 Bandung – 40272. The population in this study were all nurses at Pindad General Hospital, totaling 251 people. The samples used in this research were obtained using a purposive sampling technique which resulted in 72 samples. The variables studied in this research are Employee Engagement (X), OCB (Y), and Turnover Intention (Z). Data collection was carried out using questionnaires, field research and library research.

The analysis method in this research uses the Structural Equation Model (SEM) with the SmartPLS 3.2 analysis tool. The population in this study were all employees of The Logistic Companies in Jember Regency, totaling 148 people. According to Sugiyono (2018:140) the sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. The samples used in this research were obtained using a purposive sampling technique which resulted in 108 respondents.

Data Type

The type of data used in this study is quantitative qualitative data which is then processed using the SPSS version 25.0 application.

Data Source

The data source is the data obtained relating to the research conducted. This research data uses primary data and secondary data.

Data Collection Methods

There are three data collection methods used in this research: interviews, questionnaires, and heritage studies.

Variables and Measurements

Table 1 Research Variables and Indicators

Variables	Indicator	Source
Stress Work (X1)	1. Task demands 2. Role demands 3. Interpersonal demands 4. Organizational structure 5. Organizational leadership attitude	Afandi (2018: 179-180)
Load Work (X2)	1. Targets to be achieved 2. Working conditions 3. Use of working time 4. Standard of work	Putra (2016)
Satisfaction Work (X3)	1. Salary 2. The work itself 3. Coworkers 4. Bosses 5. Working conditions	Widodo (2015)
Turnover Intention (Y)	1. Often thinks of leaving 2. Possibility of finding a new job 3. Thinking about changing jobs	Kaswan (2015: 132)

Source: Data processed (2023)

In this study, the measurement technique used a Likert scale. According to Sugiyono (2018: 93) the Likert scale is used to measure the attitudes, opinions and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena. Then the indicator is used as a starting point for compiling instrument items which can be in the form of statements.

Data Analysis Method

Validity Test

The validity test aims to measure whether the questions asked are correct / valid / valid (Santoso, 2015: 205). In this study, the validity test was measured using *Pearson's product moment* correlation by correlating each question with the total score, then the correlation results were compared with the critical number at a significant level of 5%.

Reliability Test

Reliability is the extent to which the research instrument is trusted enough. The reliability test in this study used the *Cronbach's Alpha statistical* test. Where an instrument can be said to be reliable (reliable) if it has an alpha reliability coefficient of more than 0.60. With the test criteria if the *Cronbach Alpha* value ≥ 0.60 then the data is reliable, if the *Cronbach Alpha* value is ≤ 0.60 then the data is not reliable.

Data Normality Test

According to Sugiyono (2018: 79) the normality test is used to determine whether the data obtained is normally distributed or not. The normality test in this study was carried out on the sample using the *Kolmogrov-Smirnov* test by setting the degree of confidence (α) at 5%.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Ghozali (2016) states that multiple linear regression analysis is an analysis that aims to determine a relationship between variables and other variables. In multiple regression analysis, the variable that affects is called the *independent variable* (free variable) while the variable that is affected is called the dependent variable (dependent variable).

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test is a classic assumption test to test whether or not there is a correlation between independent variables. A good regression model should not have a correlation between the independent variables.

Heteroscedasticity Test

According to Ghozali (2016: 104) says that the heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in the regression model there is an inequality of variance from one observation to another, it can be said to be heteroscedasticity if the residual has an unequal variance.

Hypothesis Test

(t-test)

According to Ghozali (2016: 99) the t test aims to determine the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable partially. This test is done by comparing the t-count value with the t-table value.

(F Test)

Ghozali (2016: 96) states that testing in the hypothesis through the F test is used to see the significance of the influence of the independent variables simultaneously on the dependent variable.

IV. Results and Discussion

Validity Test

Table 2 Validity Test Results

Variable	Indicator	r count	r table	Ket
X1	X1_1	0.568	0.3120	Valid
	X1_2	0.336	0.3120	Valid
	X1_3	0.655	0.3120	Valid
	X1_4	0.605	0.3120	Valid
	X1_5	0.504	0.3120	Valid
X2	X2_1	0.49	0.3120	Valid
	X2_2	0.696	0.3120	Valid
	X2_3	0.776	0.3120	Valid
	X2_4	0.447	0.3120	Valid
X3	X3_1	0.627	0.3120	Valid
	X3_2	0.878	0.3120	Valid
	X3_3	0.934	0.3120	Valid
	X3_4	0.93	0.3120	Valid
	X3_5	0.888	0.3120	Valid
Y	Y_1	0.852	0.3120	Valid
	Y_2	0.947	0.3120	Valid
	Y_3	0.79	0.3120	Valid

Source: data processed (2023)

Reliability Test

Table 3 Reliability Test Results

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	R table	Information
X1	0.531	0.3120	Reliable
X2	0.438	0.3120	Reliable
X3	0.907	0.3120	Reliable
Y	0.826	0.3120	Reliable

Source: data processed (2023)

According to Joko Widiyanto (2010: 43) explains that the basis for decision making in the reliability test is if the *Cronbach's Alpha* value > r table then the questionnaire is declared reliable.

Data Normality Test

Table 4 Data Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogrov-Smirnov Test	
Unstandardized Residual	
N	108
Asymp. Sig (2-tailed)	.200 ^{c,d}

Source: Data processed (2023)

Based on the table above, it is stated that the Asymp Sig (2-tailed) value is 0.200 so the significant value is $0.200 > 0.05$, thus the data from the results of the questionnaire that has been distributed to respondents is said to be normally distributed data.

Table 5 Multiple Linier Regression Analysis Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients	
		B	Std. Error
1	(Constant)	8.324	2.935
	X1	.381	.178
	X2	.085	.212
	X3	-.457	.105

Source: Data processed (2023)

The results of the multiple linear regression analysis test in Table 6 show the coefficient values in the multiple linear regression equation obtained as follows:

$$Y = 8.324 + 0.381 X1 + 0.085 X2 + (-0.457) X3 + e$$

- The constant (a) is 8.324 which indicates that if the variable work stress (X1), workload (X2), and job satisfaction (X3) is 0, then the value of *Turnover Intention* (Y) is 8.324...
- The work stress variable (X1) has a positive effect on *turnover intention* (Y) of 0.381 so that if there is an increase in the work stress variable (X1) by 1%, it will increase the level of *turnover intention* (Y) by 0.381.
- The workload variable (X2) has a positive effect on the *turnover intention variable* (Y) of 0.085 so that if there is an increase in the workload variable (X2) by 1%, it will increase *turnover intention* (Y) by 0.085.
- The job satisfaction variable (X3) has a negative effect on the *turnover intention variable* (Y) of 0.457 so that if there is an increase in the job satisfaction variable (X3) by 1%, it will reduce the value of *turnover intention* (Y) by 0.457.

Multicollinearity Test

The results of SPSS output, the tolerance value of the work stress variable (X1) is 0.692, this value is greater than 0.1. The VIF value of work stress (X1) is 1.446, this value is smaller than 10. The tolerance value of the workload variable (X2) is 0.603, this value is greater than 0.1. The VIF value of workload (X2) is 1.658, this value is smaller than 10. The tolerance value of the job satisfaction variable (X3) is 0.775, this value is greater than 0.1. The VIF value of job satisfaction (X3) is 1.290, this value is smaller than 10. These three results all variables show a tolerance value greater than 0.1 and a VIF value smaller than 10. so it can be concluded that the regression model in this study does not occur multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The results of the analysis show that the significance of variable X1 (work stress) is 0.934, the value is greater than 0.05. This value indicates that this data does not have heteroscedasticity. The significance value of variable X2 (workload) is 0.814, this value is greater than 0.05. This value indicates that this data does not have heteroscedasticity. The significance value of variable X3 (job satisfaction) is 0.691, this value is smaller than 0.05. This value indicates that the data does not have heteroscedasticity.

Hypothesis Test (t Test)

Table 6 Results of the t-test

Varia Bell	T table	T Count	Sig	Ket
(X1)	2.02809	2,146	0,039	H0 rejected
(X2)	2.02809	0,401	0,691	H0 Accepted
(X3)	2.02809	-4,474	0,000	H0 Rejected

Source: Data processed (2023)

T table is 2.02809 with N respondents 40 X variables number 3 with a significant 0.05

1) The effect of job stress on *turnover intention*

Significant tests with decision-making criteria:

It is known that the t value is 2.146 and the t table is 2.02809. So, $2.146 > 2.02809$, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that the work stress variable has a significant effect on *turnover intention*. So it can be concluded that H_1 is accepted.

2) The effect of workload on *turnover intention*

Significant tests with decision-making criteria:

It is known that the t value is 0.401 and t table is 2.02809. So, $0.401 < 2.02809$, H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected, which means that the workload variable has no significant effect on *turnover intention*. So it can be concluded that H_2 is rejected.

3) The effect of job satisfaction on *turnover intention*

Significant tests with decision-making criteria:

It is known that the t value is -4.374 and the t table is 2.02809. So, $-4.374 > 2.02809$, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that the job satisfaction variable has a negative and significant effect on *turnover intention*. So it can be concluded that H_3 is accepted.

Test (f)

Table 7 Test Result F

	F _{count}	F _{tabel}	Sig.	Results Test
Results	11,079	2,87	0,00	H ₀ rejected

Source: Data processed (2023)

Regarding the results of the hypothesis F test, we can know that the $F_{hitung} > F_{tabel}$ value is $11.079 > 2.87$ and for the significance value is $0.00 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the independent variables consisting of work stress, workload, and job satisfaction simultaneously affect the dependent variable, namely *turnover intention*.

V. Discussion

a) The Effect of Job Stress on *Turnover Intention*

Based on the test results of multiple linear regression analysis, it shows that job stress (X1) has a positive and significant effect on employee *turnover intention*. This can be seen from the multiple linear regression analysis through the t test which is positive with a calculated t value of 2.146 and significant at 0.039. Based on these results, it can be concluded that hypothesis 1 (one) in this study is tested and acceptable. The positive direction shows that every time there is an increase in job stress felt by employees, it will cause an increase in *turnover intention* simultaneously by 0.381 units. The higher the work stress felt by each employee, the higher the *turnover intention* will also increase, this will certainly have a bad impact on the company. The results of this study are in accordance with or support research from Saeka and Suana (2016); Monica and Putra (2017); Riani and Putra (2017); Yuda and Ardana (2017); Rijasawitri and Suana (2020), and Kristin *et al.*, (2022) show that work stress has a positive and significant effect on *turnover intention*.

Job stress variables are measured using five indicators, namely task demands, role demands, interpersonal demands, organizational structure, and the attitude of company's leaders. Job stress that occurs is high, this can be seen from employees who often get complaints from consumers because of long deliveries, besides that employees have to work twice because of the rejection of COD packages from recipients, employees are often given the task of doing work that is not their job, and also employees get pressures from superiors.

In this discussion it can be stated that job stress has a positive and significant effect on employee *turnover intention*. Based on the explanation above that high work stress felt by employees will have an impact on the company which will make employees think of leaving the company.

b) The Effect of Workload on *Turnover Intention*

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis tests, it shows that workload (X2) has a positive and insignificant effect on employee *turnover intention*. This can be seen from the multiple linear regression analysis through the t test which has a positive sign with a calculated t value of 0.401 and a significant value of 0.691 which is greater than 0.05, showing that the effect of workload on *turnover intention* is not significant. Based on these results, it can be concluded that hypothesis 2 (two) in this study is rejected. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Fuhasari (2016) which shows that workload has a positive effect and has no significant effect on *turnover intention*. This explains that if the workload increases or decreases it does not affect *turnover intention*. The results of this study are also almost in line with research from Riani and Putra (2017); Sakul (2018); Silalahi (2019); Khomariyah *et al.*, (2020); Fitriantini *et al.*, (2020); Kristin *et al.*, (2022) which shows that workload has a positive and significant effect on *turnover intention*.

Workload variables are measured using four indicators, namely targets that must be achieved, work conditions, use of working time, and work standards. The workload felt by employees is still considered reasonable, this can be seen from employees who are required to be able to do a job that is assigned every day and can be completed according to orders, employees are also required to be able to send / issue packages / goods according to predetermined targets but the time given is limited, employees are also required to keep the goods perfect.

The results showed that even though employees do busy work every day, and also the targets that must be achieved in work are too high, it does not affect *turnover intention*. When associated with the characteristics of respondents based on gender, the male gender has a great responsibility, and also the male gender is seen to be able to provide for his family so that even though the workload is felt by employees, it is still acceptable so that these things do not affect *turnover intention*. In this discussion it can be stated that workload has a positive and insignificant effect on employee *turnover intention*. High workload does not affect employee *turnover intention* in the companies.

c) The Effect of Job Satisfaction on *Turnover Intention*

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis tests, it shows that job satisfaction (X1) has a negative and significant effect on employee *turnover intention*. This can be seen from the multiple linear regression analysis through the t test which is negative with a calculated t value of -4.374 and significant at 0.000. Based on these results, it can be concluded that hypothesis 3 (three) in this study is tested and acceptable. The negative direction shows that every increase in job satisfaction felt, will cause a decrease in *turnover intention* of employees simultaneously by -0.457 units. The job satisfaction obtained by each employee is higher, the *turnover intention* will decrease, this certainly has a good impact on the company, meaning that the company still pays attention to its employees by providing justice and needs. The results of this study are in accordance with or support research from Saeka and Suana (2016); Monica and Putra (2017); Khomariyah *et.al.*, (2020); Rijasawitri and Suana (2020); Fitriantini *et.al.*, (2020), and Kristin *et.al.*, (2022) show that job satisfaction has a negative effect on *turnover intention*.

Job satisfaction variables are measured using five indicators, namely salary, work itself, coworkers, superiors, and working conditions. The job satisfaction felt is quite good, this can be seen from the questionnaires that have been answered by employees that average employee chooses a fairly satisfied answer, this can be seen from the employees feeling quite satisfied with the salary they have received, with their office colleagues, with the way the leadership provides supervision, and also with the facilities in the company.

In this discussion, it can be stated that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on employee *turnover intention*. Based on the explanation above that high job satisfaction obtained by employees will have a good impact on the company which will make employees stay in the company.

d) The Effect of Job Stress, Workload, and Job Satisfaction on *Turnover Intention*

Based on the multiple linear regression test, the constant value is positive at 8.324 which shows the positive effect of the independent variables, namely work stress (X1), workload (X2), and job satisfaction (X3), the dependent variable *turnover intention* (Y). This means that if the variable value of work stress (X1), workload (X2), and job satisfaction (X3) is equal to 0, then the variable value of *turnover intention* (Y) is equal to the constant value of 8, 324. The results of the f test show a significant $0.00 < 0.05$ which can be concluded that the independent variables consisting of work stress, workload, and job satisfaction simultaneously affect the dependent variable, namely *turnover intention*. This is supported by research by Miftahur *et al.*, (2021) that workload, job satisfaction, and job stress variables simultaneously affect *turnover intention*.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion in this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Job stress (X1) has a positive and significant effect on employee *turnover intention* (Y). These results mean that high job stress felt by an employee will lead to increased *turnover intention* and have a negative impact on the company.
- Workload (X2) has a positive and insignificant effect on employee *turnover intention* (Y). These results mean that the workload felt by an employee cannot determine the high or low *turnover intention* in the company.
- Job satisfaction (X3) has a negative and significant effect on *turnover intention* (Y). These results mean that high job satisfaction obtained by an employee will reduce *turnover intention* in the company and vice versa.
- Job stress, workload, and job satisfaction have a simultaneous and significant influence on the *turnover intention* of employees, which means that if the variables of job stress and workload increase, *turnover intention* will also increase, while for job satisfaction the more it increases, *turnover intention* will decrease.

Advice

- For The Logistics Companies in Jember Regency

1) Job Stress

Based on the results of the study revealing that job stress is in the high category, the companies should pay more attention to the demands of their employees' tasks whether they are proportional to the risks of their work. The companies should also observe the tasks or roles received from each employee whether they feel they have a great responsibility for the tasks they receive. In addition, the companies also need to observe the flow of orders in the organizational structure so that there is no overlap that

makes employees uncomfortable at work. Finally, the companies can conduct evaluations every month so that employees feel more cared for.

2) Workload

Based on the results of the study revealed that workload is in the medium category, indicators that show low value results are targets that must be achieved and work standards. The low value of the target indicator that must be achieved can show that employees have ineffective working time so far. This can be seen from the results of the research questionnaire which reveals that the targets to be achieved in the work are too high and not proportional to the time period that has been set so that they have to work faster and more precisely. The companies evaluate the workload felt by employees and the estimated time given to complete the task. This is done in the hope of improving employee working time more effectively, so that the workload will be more controlled and balanced. In addition, it can also provide work comfort and safety for employees.

3) Job Satisfaction

Based on the research results revealing that job satisfaction is in the good category, the companies are expected to further improve the job satisfaction given to employees such as providing additional wages if employees are required to work overtime, besides that the companies can also create a comfortable work environment that makes employees feel safe and happy while in the office. This can help employees be more active in working and also feel happy so that employees will not think about leaving the companies.

b. For future researchers

1) This research is expected to be a reference for further research with similar topics related to work stress, workload, and job satisfaction on *turnover intention*.

2) It is hoped that future researchers can add other variables that can affect the *turnover intention variable*. This aims to find out more complex problems that can affect *turnover intention*.

3) It is hoped that future researchers will distribute questionnaires offline in order to control the answers of respondents.

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